

**ADOPTING TO HYBRID OR HAY!-BRID SET UP: COLLEGE STUDENTS'
EXPERIENCES AND SENTIMENTS FOR ACCESSING
ADMINISTRATIVE SERVICES**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 1

Pages: 83-91

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2142

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13218934

Manuscript Accepted: 07-01-2024

Adopting to Hybrid or Hay!-brid Set up: College Students' Experiences and Sentiments for Accessing Administrative Services

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the ongoing challenges of the Digital Divide in educational institutions, extending beyond mere technology availability and access. This study employed inductive-thematic analysis to investigate the experiences of 20 college students at the University of Caloocan City in accessing administrative services during the height of the pandemic. The participants included incoming and current students, as well as recent graduates who had interacted with the university's administrative services. Three main themes emerged from the analysis: limited internet access, the university's inadequate online presence, and gaps in technology skills among administrators and personnel. These findings pinpoint specific areas where the university needs to enhance its information and communication technology resources and infrastructure to better serve its students. This study adds to the ongoing discussion on the Digital Divide and underscores the need to improve technology effectiveness and utilization. The results provide valuable insights for developing policies and strategies to help educational institutions address Digital Divide challenges and support students during crises.

Keywords: *digital divide, administrative services, college students, higher education, ICT policy*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly impacted global education systems, leading to a rapid adoption of digital technology to facilitate remote learning. However, this swift transition to online education has underscored the existing digital divide and its ramifications for educational institutions (El Said, 2021). The digital gap disproportionately affects college students, as they heavily depend on technology to access vital administrative services provided by their institutions. Williamson et al. (2020) demonstrated in their study that an Internet connection is crucial for the functioning of a modern educational ecosystem. This sheds light on why millions of students face challenges in continuing their virtual education due to inadequate digital resources.

Clearly, the COVID-19 pandemic has exposed old looming problems, particularly the reality that there is a huge disparity in countries' digital readiness for virtual learning and the exacerbation of existing inequalities between privileged and unprivileged learners, which is a real threat to their learning continuity (Ryan, 2023). Hence, the situation of virtual learning in the country is a blatant case of the digital divide. Simbulan (2020) stated that Filipino students and teachers who are already in remote learning are experiencing a digital divide. There are students who have limited access to computers or the internet because of their uneven socioeconomic status. Issues in mental health were also mentioned as a concern for both students and teachers, as they are both affected by the uncertainty (Fontenelle-Tereshchu, 2021). Shutting down schools in the middle of a pandemic worsens the digital divide, which leaves poorer children with less internet access falling behind their wealthier and more connected classmates (Lee, 2020).

Over three million students were forced to discontinue their basic education during the 2020–2021 school year ("the pandemic school year"). This figure is comparable to the population of Quezon City, Philippines (2.94 million), indicating that despite school efforts to encourage registration and enrolment, the shift of the traditional June school year opening to October, and the "no student left behind" government campaign in the midst of COVID-19, there were still students who were unable to register or continue their studies. According to a discussion paper by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS), only 1per cent of poor households, 6per cent of low-income households, and 27per cent of lower-middle-income households have a computer (Uaminal, 2021).

The problems mentioned in the digital divide are no different at the University of Caloocan City (UCC). Aside from the challenges that students encounter during online classes, most, if not all, transactions for its administrative services are now done online as well. Administrative offices such as the Registrar's Office, Records Section, Accounting Office, and Admissions Office were reached online for their services. Similar to other schools that utilize traditional teaching and learning strategies, UCC was forced to have "online counterparts" of its offices to continuously serve its students. Traditionally, the university responds to requests requiring students or applicants to be physically present in the office, but because of the pandemic, the school transacts with its students online. For instance, when a graduating student requests a True Copy of Grades (TCG), they have to go to the Registrar's Office to fill out a Request Form, proceed to the Accounting Office to pay, and then wait for the Records Section to pull out the file being requested. It normally takes 5-7 business days before the office provides a document, depending on its kind.

Research Objective

The objective of this study is to investigate the extent to which the digital divide has affected college students' access to administrative services during the pandemic and to identify the specific challenges they face when attempting to access these services. Furthermore,

the study seeks to provide recommendations for improving the information and communication technology resources of the school based on the lessons and opportunities that arise from these challenges. By doing so, it aims to contribute to the existing literature on the impact of the digital divide in educational institutions and to provide practical insights that may be useful to schools and other stakeholders as they work to address this issue.

Literature Review

Digital Divide: A Philippine Context

The digital divide refers to the gap between individuals or groups who have access to and effectively use digital technologies and those who do not (Van Dijk, 2020). It is a complex issue that is influenced by multiple factors, including socioeconomic status, geographic location, age, and gender. According to Zickuhr and Smith (2012), access to the internet is a crucial determinant of digital inclusion. However, internet access alone does not guarantee digital inclusion, as individuals also need to have the skills, motivation, and opportunity to use digital technologies effectively.

According to the Center for Digital Inclusion (2020, cited in van Dijk, 2005), the "digital divide" began as part of the discussions of researchers and policymakers in the 1990s. It is based on a comparative view of social and information inequality and assumes that the advantages of ICT access and usage are connected with the negative consequences of non-access and usage. It is also emphasized that the metaphor of the digital divide has a lot of flaws. To begin, the referenced split is more of a spectrum between groups of individuals who use computers and the Internet for everyday work and others who do not. Second, the divide between the two groups is difficult to overcome. Finally, contrary to the notion that the gap is about disparities between those who are included and those who are excluded, the difference is more visible in most inequalities in access to digital technology. Finally, the notion that the split is a static situation is incorrect, as these gaps are always moving. Adding to these insights, Nielsen (2006) delineates the three stages of digital divide beyond mere access. Stage 1, the Economic Divide, acknowledges the decreasing cost of computers yet highlights ongoing challenges in affordability, particularly in developing countries. Stage 2, the Usability Divide, emphasizes the complexity of technology, impacting users' ability to harness its full potential. Stage 3, the Empowerment Divide, points to the disparity in leveraging digital opportunities, highlighting participation inequalities and challenges in fully utilizing digital tools even when accessible.

Contreras (2020) revealed in a finding that in order to offer online learning, online connectivity is required and that the country's low internet connectivity is a factor in resistance to online learning. Lower-income students who have difficulty accessing the Internet are also deemed divided. He also noted that in 2017, it is anticipated that 64 million individuals in the Philippines will have an internet connection, with 51.5 million of these people using social media. 81 per cent of those who were online were between the ages of 18 and 24 (college-age). In this group, the digital divide that was explained is how this group will be able to "appreciate the use of the internet for learning purposes and not just for entertainment, leisure, and social networking." He added that another digital divide is about older people who are considered teachers and educators because they are from these age groups. According to statistics, just 12% of persons aged 55 and up can use the internet; this low number explains why older people have a lesser online presence since they either reject or are unable to. This will have an impact on online learning, as teachers will be unable to provide a quality online education because they are unfamiliar with or have no interest in learning skills about the new technology that is currently employed in online classes.

Esteban and Cruz's (2021) study found that "During a pandemic, a digital divide is wider, and the negative effects created by COVID-19 on students become more obvious." This was discovered using statistics from 264 people studying in Technology for Teaching and Learning classes at the Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology's College of Education during the first semester of the 2020-2021 school year, as well as demographic characteristics such as residential. According to the findings of a study, annual family income is a predictor of the digital divide since access to the internet is limited in disadvantaged kids' households due to a lower budget for internet fees. Parental educational success is also a predictor of the digital divide, as respondents with higher education levels have greater internet access. Even though 202 students (76.52 percent) own smartphones for online study, there are still students who are unable to get online due to device limitations. There are pupils who are having trouble accessing online educational resources because they have low-tech gadgets. Nine (3.41%) still utilize keypad cell phones, and one (0.38%) doesn't even own any gadgets. With an average upload speed of 2.7 Mbps and a typical mobile broadband transfer rate of 8.5 Mbps in the Philippines, 147 students (55.68%) used mobile data. These findings are consistent with the weekly online expenses, where 110 students (41.67%) managed to spend Php 100–150 on internet spending each week, 90 students (34.09%) consumed Php 160–200, and 58 students (21.97%) spent Php 200 or more. This demonstrates that students devote a significant amount of money and time to accessing the internet and attending their online classes, and unfortunately, 35 students (13.26 per cent) do not have access to the web at home. Aside from that, when questioned about the factors influencing their ICT and internet use, students responded with limited access or slow internet connection in an area (43.63 per cent), financial capacity (26.70 per cent), type of ICT device (14.49 per cent), lack of technical knowledge (6.11 per cent), no accessible device to use (4.54 per cent), insufficient parental assistance (4.01 per cent), and power interference (0.52 per cent).

Apart from connectivity issues, the lack of access to devices is also a major obstacle to online learning. According to Kuhfeld et al. (2020), about 15 to 16 million K–12 students in the United States lack home internet or computer access. This issue is further exacerbated for students from low-income families or rural areas, who have limited resources to acquire the necessary technology for

online learning. Similarly, a study by Bekova et al., (2021) found that the transition to online learning in higher education institutions has exposed disparities in student access to technology, with students from underrepresented groups and low-income families being the most affected.

Impact of the Digital Divide on Educational Institutions

The digital divide has serious consequences for educational institutions, especially when it comes to providing access to online instructional resources and administrative services. According to Dong, et.al (2020), the digital gap had a substantial influence on Indian students' capacity to engage in online lessons during the epidemic. According to the findings, students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds had substantial difficulty accessing the internet and digital devices, limiting their capacity to engage in online classes. Moreover, research on the influence of COVID-19 on education in China conducted by Gou & Wan (2020) discovered that the digital divide increased pre-existing disparities in the area. The survey cited a lack of internet connectivity, low digital skills, and insufficient teacher preparation as major issues.

The digital divide impacts not only online learning but also access to administrative services such as registration, academic counselling, and financial assistance for college students. According to Rofiah et al., (2022), the digital gap has hampered Thai university students' capacity to access administrative services during the epidemic. According to the survey, main barriers to obtaining these services include a lack of technology infrastructure, insufficient technical help, and low digital abilities. In the Philippines, a study by Palvia et.al., (2018) found that the digital divide had significant implications for college students' access to administrative services. The study revealed that students faced challenges in accessing online registration systems, online grading systems, and other online administrative services due to a lack of access to reliable internet connections and digital devices.

The challenges faced by college students in accessing administrative services during the pandemic provide opportunities for schools to improve their Information and Communication Technology (ICT) resources. A study by Sari and Sari (2021) identified the potential for universities to use e-government platforms to improve the delivery of administrative services. It was discovered that the usage of e-government platforms could improve administrative services' efficiency and accessibility, especially for students from rural or remote places. In a related study, Moliner et al. (2021) found that in order to facilitate online learning and administrative services, schools may be able to enhance their digital infrastructure and teacher preparation. The study discovered that, especially in light of the pandemic, efficient teacher preparation programs and the use of digital technology might improve the standard of instruction and administrative services.

The lack of access to devices is also a significant barrier to online learning. A survey by the Rice (2020) revealed that 24per cent of households in the country have no access to a computer, and 40per cent have no access to the internet. In addition, Rotas and Cahapay (2020) noted that the pandemic has highlighted the digital divide in Philippine schools, with public schools struggling to provide students with the necessary equipment and connectivity for online learning. The digital gap impacts students' access to administrative services in educational institutions in addition to connectivity and device-related problems. According to a study conducted in Nigeria by Akanbi & Akanbi (2012), students' access to information and services offered by universities, such as course registration, library services, and fee payments, is impacted by the digital divide. The survey also showed that students in rural areas and those from low-income families are especially impacted by this problem. In a similar vein, a South Korean study by Lee and Im (2020) discovered that students' access to administrative services like online course registration and academic advising is impacted by the digital gap in education.

Given the issues caused by the digital divide, educational institutions have made steps to solve the problem. One solution is to equip students with the required technology and connectivity for online learning (Stewart, 2004). For instance, the Emergency Broadband Benefit Program, established by the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) in the United States, provides low-income households with a \$50 monthly subsidy for an internet connection (Kuhfeld et al., 2020). Comparably, the Philippine government has started a number of programs to give students access to digital devices and the internet. These programs include the Department of Information and Communications Technology's Free Wi-Fi for All program and the Department of Education's Learning Continuity Plan (Department of Education, 2020).

Another strategy to address the digital divide is to improve the design and delivery of online learning and administrative services. A study by Kim and Kwon (2020) in South Korea recommended the development of a user-friendly platform for online learning and administrative services to bridge the digital divide. The study also suggested the provision of training and support for students and faculty members to enhance their digital literacy skills. In summary, the digital divide poses significant challenges to students' access to administrative services in educational institutions, particularly during the pandemic. This issue is further exacerbated by the lack of access to technology and connectivity, as well as the limited digital literacy skills of some students. In order to mitigate the digital divide, it is imperative for educational institutions to provide students with adequate technology and connectivity for effective online learning, and to enhance the design and delivery of online administrative services.

The impact of the digital divide on educational institutions has been highlighted in various studies, specifically on college students' access to administrative services during the pandemic (Shin & Hickey, 2021; Rafiq et.al., 2021). The literature review reveals that the digital divide poses challenges on technology access, Internet connectivity, and technology skills. The review also emphasizes the

importance of information and communication technology (ICT) in addressing the digital divide and enabling students to access remote administrative services. Furthermore, the lack of physical access, skills, and knowledge of students towards ICT has intensified the gaps in the digital divide during the pandemic. As such, conducting qualitative studies that explore the experiences of Filipino students can supplement the available information and aid in the development of policies that maximize an organization's existing ICT resources.

Methodology

This study utilized a descriptive-interpretive case study research design to investigate the experiences of college students at the University of Caloocan City in accessing administrative services during the pandemic. The study population included incoming students (applicants), current students, and recent graduates who had interacted with the university's administrative services. A purposive sampling technique was employed to recruit 20 participants, comprising three incoming freshmen (student applicants), five incoming second-year students, six incoming third-year students, three incoming fourth-year students, and three recent graduates.

The descriptive-interpretive case study approach was chosen to provide an in-depth understanding of the participants' experiences. This methodology allows for the exploration of complex phenomena within their real-life context. It involves collecting detailed information through various data sources, including interviews, observations, and documents. In this study, in-depth interviews were conducted with each participant to elucidate their unique experiences and perspectives regarding the administrative services of the school during the height of pandemic where no physical contact were being imposed and most (if not all) school transactions are done on hybrid or remote manner.

Inductive thematic analysis was employed to identify emergent themes and patterns within the data. Initial codes were organized into matrices within a dendrogram to extract significant statements and materials from the interviews. Participants were informed about the research's purpose and methodology prior to the interviews, and their informed consent was obtained. The qualitative data analysis software NVivo was utilized to process the interview data. Iterative rounds of coding and categorization were performed until data saturation was achieved. To enhance the validity and credibility of the study, the findings were triangulated with relevant literature.

Results and Discussion

Based on the results, it is evident that the majority of the participants experienced the negative impacts of the digital divide, despite having basic resources for accessing the university's administrative services. The participants' narratives demonstrated the inefficiencies and shortcomings of the existing processes, which further exacerbated the challenges they faced in terms of accessing technology, such as cell phones, internet, laptops, desktops, and so on.

Figure 1. Challenges in Accessing Administrative Services

Free Data means No Data

"Free Data" is a promotional offering by some mobile network providers in the Philippines that provides free or unlimited data access to certain apps or websites, without consuming the subscriber's mobile data allowance. The types of websites or apps that are included in the free data offerings can vary, but they typically include popular social media platforms, messaging apps, and other online services.

The availability and terms of free data offers can vary depending on the mobile network provider and the specific promotional offer. Some offers may be limited to certain subscribers, such as new customers or those with specific mobile plans, while others may be available to all subscribers.

Free data offers have become popular in the Philippines as a way for mobile network providers to attract and retain customers by providing them with free access to popular online services without incurring additional data charges. However, some consumer advocates have raised concerns that these types of offers can be deceptive or may encourage excessive use of certain online services. It is worth noting that while free data offers may provide subscribers with access to certain websites or apps without incurring additional data charges, they do not necessarily provide unlimited data access overall. Subscribers may still be subject to data caps or other usage restrictions, and additional data charges may still apply for usage outside of the free data offering.

According to the study, the majority of students (17 out of 20) had limited access to Wi-Fi internet service, which put them at a disadvantage. As a result, they relied on "free data" to stay updated on school announcements and communicate with their classmates who had access to broadband connections. In some cases, students had to go outside their homes, even during curfews, to access Wi-Fi from their neighbours.

P11: "...sobrang hirap, lalo na kapag walang internet. Ang hassle talaga kapag putol-putol yung connection, tapos malapit na yung deadline para sa pag-fill up ng [form]. Kailangan pa namin maghintay ng madaling araw para ma-process yun." (...it's really a struggle, especially when there's no internet. It's really inconvenient when my connection keeps getting cut, and the deadline for filling up the [form] is coming up. We have to wait until the early hours of the morning to process it.)

The COVID-19 pandemic has shifted the focus of the digital divide issue from the mere availability of technology to its effectiveness in facilitating remote learning and administrative services. Basic tools such as mobile phones and average internet connectivity are no longer sufficient to meet the requirements of students to effectively complete their coursework. In Caloocan, prior to the pandemic, public Wi-Fi was installed by Globe Telecom in certain hotspot areas to address connectivity issues. However, these areas still fall short of meeting the needs of the community as they only offer an hour of access that refreshes the next day. This has led to many students resorting to free data services for their online learning needs.

"Free data" programs in the Philippines have been implemented by telecommunication companies as a response to the increasing need for internet connectivity during the COVID-19 pandemic. These programs offer users a limited amount of free data to access basic online services such as educational materials, health information, and government services.

While these programs are aimed at addressing the digital divide by providing free access to the internet, they have limitations that may exacerbate existing inequalities. For example, the amount of free data is often limited, and once it is consumed, users must pay for additional data. This can be a significant burden for low-income families who cannot afford to purchase additional data. Furthermore, the programs may not address the underlying issue of unequal access to technology, as many households may not have the necessary devices to access the internet even if they have free data.

"Affordability" is also one of the problems that emerged when access to the internet is talked about. The respondents (students) came from low-income families and do not have the capacity to subscribe to an internet provider. Similar to their basic needs, mobile data has to be well budgeted so that they can make use of it fully. It is believed that the internet at night-time is faster than in the daytime that's why most of them have to stay up late when they need to finish an activity online.

Official Online Platform

When schools closed their doors in March 2020, they had to quickly pivot to remote instruction and provide students with online access to academic and administrative services. Schools sent learning packets home or held online classes to finish the remaining school year, while creating online counterparts of their offices to continue providing necessary services. Social media platforms, particularly Facebook, were used to disseminate information and announcements on how to access needed services. However, creating an online platform is only one part of the equation; ensuring it is active and efficient presents a separate set of challenges.

During the interviews, all of the students reported difficulties in comprehending and adhering to the new administrative procedures implemented by the school. Confusion existed within the university community regarding where parents and students could obtain specific updates from, as the official publication (The New Crossroads) was more frequently updated than the school's official website and Facebook page. Despite the school issuing statements and notifications on their official website, the student publication was more active in disseminating information to students. Consequently, the respondents no longer found the school's official website useful, which created more confusion than assistance.

Some respondents had to verify the authenticity of announcements and instructions posted online by going to the school. The University of Caloocan City gives priority to student applicants who are residents of Caloocan and graduates of Caloocan high schools, as it is funded by the local government. Applicants who wish to enrol at the university must provide additional documentation, such as a voter's ID, a letter of intent, and their parents' voter's ID. One incoming freshman expressed during the interview that they had to take the risk of visiting the school in person to verify if the information posted online about the application requirements was true and accurate.

P9: "...hindi sila [school personnel] sumasagot sa mga comments namin sa post [tungkol sa requirements para sa freshmen applicants]. Kaya pumunta na lang kami ng mama ko sa school para i-confirm kung anong documents yung kailangan namin i-submit kasi hindi kami graduate sa Caloocan [high school]." (...they [school personnel] do not reply to our comments on the post [about the requirements for freshmen applicants]. That's why my mom and I went to the school to confirm what documents we need to submit when we did not graduate from a Caloocan [high school].)

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought to the forefront the issue of the digital divide, which extends beyond the mere availability of technology to encompass its effective use. While it is crucial to provide students with the necessary technology and internet connectivity to bridge the digital divide, it is equally important to maximize the potential of these resources to achieve optimal outcomes. Thus, educational institutions such as schools must craft comprehensive ICT plans that not only focus on providing students with access to technology, but also on developing their technology skills and promoting the effective use of technology in both academic and administrative settings. This can include measures such as investing in teacher training and support, creating user-friendly online platforms, and ensuring that students have the necessary resources and support to use technology effectively. By prioritizing these aspects, educational institutions can help ensure that students are able to benefit fully from the resources available to them and overcome the challenges posed by the digital divide.

“Age Gap = Skills Gap”

It is noticeable that today’s internet is dominated by the younger crowd who surprisingly have an easy understanding and appreciation of technology. Without a manual, they can manoeuvre and get familiarized with the technology of today’s time. Besides access to technology, “age” and “generation” has to be considered as well as factor in contributing to Digital Divide. There are certain generations or age groups that are still demotivated and reluctant to use the technology because they are not “used” to it and they have a hard time adapting to it.

In the study, it was found that the age and capacity of an office staff handling the school’s online page is a factor that contributes to the challenges that the students experienced when they are accessing the office. In addition, it amplifies the issue of resources of the university in ICT that was not fully maximized. Most of the staff and officers of the administrative offices of the school belong in their 40s to ’60s; younger staff are mostly in “casual” employment and were laid off because of the pandemic, leading the offices to have “older” employees. Staff who are now working on the online pages of the offices are not properly trained to results to slow responses of the online pages to its inquiries.

The age gap and skills gap are significant challenges contributing to the digital divide in the Philippines for several reasons. Firstly, the younger generation, particularly those residing in urban areas, are more likely to have access to technology and digital resources compared to the older generation. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020), 45.3per cent of individuals aged 15-24 years old use the internet, compared to only 5.7per cent of those aged 60 years and above. Secondly, there is a skills gap in the use of digital technologies, particularly among the older generation. While younger individuals have grown up with technology, many older adults may have limited knowledge and skills in using digital devices and applications. This lack of digital literacy can make it difficult for them to access and utilize online services and resources.

During the interview, one of the respondents shared her sentiments when she found out that her documents for enrolment weren’t processed yet despite submitting her requirements earlier than most of her classmates. Alarmed and confused, she followed it up to the office through e-mail and through Facebook Messenger; unfortunately, no one responded that’s why she decided to come to school and personally check what happened. She found out that her message was accidentally “archived” and the person assigned in receiving the e-mails is not familiar with the feature. Despite the frustration, she still followed the advice to “resubmit” the requirements to process her enrolment.

The age gap and skills gap are further compounded by socioeconomic factors. Those who come from lower-income households may have limited access to technology, which can exacerbate the digital divide. Moreover, even if they do have access, they may not have the resources to acquire the necessary digital skills and knowledge to use these technologies effectively. Overall, addressing the age and skills gap is critical in bridging the digital divide in the Philippines. This can be done through initiatives such as providing digital literacy training and resources, particularly to the older generation, and making digital technologies and resources more accessible to those from low-income households.

Conclusions

The COVID-19 pandemic has starkly highlighted the digital divide, underscoring persistent challenges in access to technology, its effective utilization, and the necessary skills. This study identifies three critical themes: access to internet technology, resource maximization, and skill development, which are particularly pronounced among students from low-income backgrounds. Addressing these issues requires comprehensive action from policymakers and higher education institutions.

Bridging the Gap

Policymakers are urged to prioritize the development of comprehensive strategies aimed at ensuring equitable access to technology,

particularly internet connectivity. This involves not only expanding infrastructure in underserved areas but also implementing affordability measures to make internet services accessible to marginalized communities. Addressing barriers to access is fundamental to reducing disparities in digital inclusion across socioeconomic strata. In addition to enhancing access, efforts should focus on bridging digital literacy gaps. Many individuals, particularly from low-income backgrounds, may lack the necessary skills to effectively utilize digital resources. Policymakers should invest in programs that provide training and support in digital literacy, empowering individuals to navigate online platforms, access educational content, and engage in digital communication effectively.

Enhancing Institutional Capacities and Knowledge Tools

Higher education institutions, exemplified by the University of Caloocan City, must conduct a thorough assessment of their existing technological resources to optimize current capabilities before investing in new infrastructure. By strategically allocating resources and implementing capacity-building activities, institutions can better support students and staff in leveraging technology for academic and administrative purposes. This includes providing targeted training programs aimed at enhancing users' technological competencies, ensuring proficiency in navigating digital platforms, managing online resources, and adapting to evolving technological landscapes effectively. During crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, institutions are urged to adopt innovative approaches to service delivery, such as implementing robust knowledge management tools like frequently asked questions (FAQs) sections on institutional websites. These tools enhance accessibility to critical information, reduce reliance on physical visits, facilitate remote access to essential services, and thereby safeguard community health while ensuring continuous support for students and staff alike.

Continuous Evaluation and Adaptation

Continuous evaluation of policies and practices plays a pivotal role in enabling institutions to adapt promptly to evolving technological landscapes and evolving user demands. Through regular reviews, institutions can pinpoint areas for enhancement, refine existing strategies, and align initiatives with emerging trends in digital education and service delivery. Cultivating a culture of iterative improvement is essential for institutions to effectively navigate challenges presented by the digital era and enhance overall institutional efficacy. The study underscores the imperative for policymakers and educational institutions to collaborate comprehensively in addressing the digital divide. This involves prioritizing equitable access to technology, enhancing institutional capacities, leveraging knowledge management tools, and promoting ongoing evaluation and adaptation. These integrated efforts are designed to mitigate disparities and ensure fair opportunities for all students, regardless of socioeconomic backgrounds, underscoring the critical importance of proactive planning and strategic investment in advancing digital inclusion and educational equity, both locally and globally.

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